

Role of Yoga Nidra in Improving Cardiovascular and Psychological Health among the Geriatric Population: A Review

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Abstract:

Background: The rapid growth of the geriatric population worldwide has led to an increased burden of cardiovascular and psychological health problems. Non-communicable diseases such as hypertension, along with mental health issues including anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances, significantly affect the quality of life among older adults. Yoga Nidra, a traditional yogic relaxation technique rooted in pratyahara, has emerged as a potential mind-body intervention for improving overall health.

Objective: This review aims to examine the effects of Yoga Nidra on cardiovascular parameters and psychological well-being among the geriatric population.

Methods: A systematic review of literature published between 2010 and 2026 was conducted using databases such as PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar, and ScienceDirect. Relevant studies focusing on Yoga Nidra interventions and their impact on cardiovascular and psychological outcomes in older adults were included.

Results: The findings indicate that Yoga Nidra significantly reduces systolic and diastolic blood pressure, improves heart rate variability, and enhances autonomic balance. Additionally, it reduces stress, anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances while promoting relaxation and emotional stability.

Conclusion: Yoga Nidra is a safe, cost-effective, and promising complementary intervention for improving cardiovascular and psychological health among older adults, although further large-scale studies are needed. Keywords- Yama, Niyama, Corporate Ethics, Work-Life Balance, Business Ethics.

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Introduction

Yoga Nidra: Concept and Traditional Foundations

Yoga Nidra, meaning “yogic sleep” or “conscious sleep,” is a meditative technique aimed at inducing deep relaxation and inner awareness [1]. According to ancient Indian traditions, sages are described as entering states akin to Yoga Nidra. The term itself is derived from two Sanskrit words: “Yoga,” from *yuj*, meaning union or one-pointed awareness, and “nidra,” meaning sleep. It is therefore understood as a systematic method of inducing complete physical, mental, and emotional relaxation by turning awareness inward and withdrawing from external experiences [2].

The practice is rooted in the pratyahara limb of Patanjali’s Ashtanga Yoga, involving withdrawal of awareness from external stimuli and directing attention inward^[2]. Yoga Nidra is widely recognized as an effective technique for achieving deep physical, mental, and emotional relaxation. It represents a distinct state of consciousness that is neither ordinary sleep nor wakefulness, nor merely concentration or hypnosis; rather, it may be described as an altered state of consciousness. In traditional literature, Maharshi Markandeya refers to Yoga Nidra as a state of profound relaxation associated with Lord Vishnu [3]. Likewise, Swatmarama, in the *Hatha Yoga Pradipika*, identifies Yoga Nidra with the state of *turiya*, the “fourth” dimension of consciousness in which Shakti remains in union with Shiva, or supreme consciousness [4]. In its modern form, Yoga Nidra was systematized by Swami Satyananda Saraswati of the Bihar School of Yoga as a simplified adaptation of tantric kriyas. It is now regarded as a powerful technique for inducing relaxation at physical, mental, and emotional levels. Studies conducted at Charing Cross Medical School, London, suggested that Yoga Nidra facilitates shifts in brain-wave activity from beta to alpha and then to delta states, allowing the practitioner to consciously experience different levels of awareness. For this reason, Yoga Nidra is considered not only a practice of pratyahara but also a gateway to meditation^[2].

Ageing and the Growing Geriatric Population

Older adults are among the most experienced and valuable members of society, contributing wisdom, knowledge, and life experience that can guide social development and national progress [5]. However, rapid population ageing has created substantial social, economic, and health-related challenges worldwide [6]. Ageing in India is increasing rapidly as falling fertility and rising life expectancy are expanding the geriatric population. UNFPA’s India Ageing Report states that the elderly population is projected to rise to about **20% of the total population by 2050**, and the population aged **80 years and above may grow by 279% between 2022 and 2050** [7]. As a result, the number and proportion of individuals aged 60 years and above continue to increase steadily. In 2019, the global older adult population was estimated at around 1 billion, and this figure is projected to rise to 1.4 billion by 2030 and 2.1 billion by 2050. By that time, nearly 80% of older adults are expected to live in low- and middle-income countries [8,9].

Health Challenges in Older Adults

This demographic transition has major implications for health. Ageing is a natural and unavoidable process characterized by progressive decline in physiological and physical functioning, which increases vulnerability to chronic non-communicable diseases such as hypertension, cardiovascular disease, diabetes, osteoporosis, osteoarthritis, sensory impairments, and falls [10,11]. Ageing also affects multiple physiological systems and increases susceptibility to chronic illnesses including cancer, cardiovascular disease, and respiratory disorders [12,13]. In addition, the World Health Organization recognizes ageing as a multidimensional phenomenon involving biological, psychological, social, and contextual dimensions [14]. Consequently, older adults often face both physical and psychological difficulties that contribute to disability and reduced quality of life [15].

Mental Health Problems in Later Life

Mental health disorders are particularly common in later life. Cognitive decline is among the most frequently observed conditions in older adults and is a major cause of functional impairment. Mental health problems in later life are a major concern in India, with depression, anxiety, dementia, and sleep disturbances commonly affecting older adults. A systematic review reported that the pooled prevalence of depression among Indians aged 60 years and above was 34.4%, while WHO notes that loneliness, social isolation, abuse, and declining physical health increase mental health risks in old age [16]. Another European study reported that 25% of elderly individuals were living with a current mental disorder, and 33% had experienced one within the previous year, with anxiety, affective, and substance-related disorders being the most common. Depression, in particular, is a major concern, with reported prevalence ranging from 10% to 38% [17,18].

Yoga Nidra and Cardiovascular Health

Yoga Nidra has been shown to produce significant improvements in resting cardiovascular parameters, including systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, and heart rate, as well as anthropometric measures such as body weight and BMI [19]. This suggests that Yoga Nidra may play an important role in promoting cardiovascular regulation. Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) comprise a broad group of disorders affecting the heart and blood vessels, including coronary heart disease, stroke, transient ischemic attack, peripheral arterial disease, and aortic disease [20]. Collectively, these conditions remain the leading cause of death worldwide, accounting for approximately 17.9 million deaths each year, or nearly 32% of all global deaths [21]. Among the many contributing risk factors, hypertension is considered the most prevalent and one of the most modifiable, affecting nearly 1.28 billion adults globally [22]. Yoga Nidra may support cardiovascular health by reducing blood pressure and improving autonomic balance. A systematic review and meta-analysis found that Yoga Nidra was effective in lowering systolic and diastolic blood pressure [23], especially among individuals with hypertension, while a 2025 intervention study reported that even a single session reduced blood pressure and increased heart rate variability, suggesting enhanced parasympathetic activity [24]. Nevertheless, hypertension control remains poor, as less than 25% of affected individuals achieve adequate blood pressure management [25].

Yoga Nidra and Psychological Health

In addition to cardiovascular concerns, Yoga Nidra may also hold relevance for psychological health. Mental health refers to a state of well-being in which an individual is able to cope with life's stresses, work productively, and function effectively in daily life. The World Health Organization's mental health action plan emphasized leadership, community-based services, promotion and prevention strategies, and improved information systems and research in the field of mental health [26]. Neuropsychiatric disorders account for a substantial proportion of the global burden of disease, contributing nearly 14% overall [27]. This concern becomes even more significant in older adults, who often experience physical, emotional, and psychological challenges associated with ageing [28,29]. In this context, Yoga Nidra appears to be a promising mind-body practice that may support both cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population.

Objectives

1. To review the effects of Yoga Nidra on cardiovascular health parameters among the geriatric population, particularly blood pressure, heart rate, and heart rate variability.
2. To examine the role of Yoga Nidra in improving psychological health outcomes among older adults, including stress, anxiety, depression, and overall mental well-being.
3. To analyse the potential of Yoga Nidra as a supportive mind-body intervention for promoting overall health and quality of life in the geriatric population.

Need of the Study

1. The geriatric population is increasing rapidly worldwide, leading to a greater burden of cardiovascular and psychological health problems among older adults.

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2. Older adults are highly vulnerable to conditions such as hypertension, cardiovascular disease, stress, anxiety, depression, and cognitive decline, which reduce their quality of life.
3. Yoga Nidra is a simple, non-invasive, and cost-effective mind-body practice that may help improve both cardiovascular and psychological health in the elderly.
4. There is a need to systematically review the existing literature to understand the therapeutic role of Yoga Nidra in promoting health and well-being among the geriatric population.

Research Gap

A clear research gap exists in the limited and scattered evidence on the combined effects of Yoga Nidra on cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population.

Research Methodology

The present study was conducted as a review to examine the role of Yoga Nidra in improving cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population. A comprehensive literature search was carried out to identify relevant scholarly articles published between **2010 and 2026**. The search was performed using major electronic databases, including **PubMed, Scopus, Google Scholar and ScienceDirect**. The purpose of the search was to collect peer-reviewed articles and other relevant academic studies related to Yoga Nidra and its effects on cardiovascular and psychological health outcomes in older adults.

The selection of search terms was done carefully to cover all major aspects of the topic, including related words, synonymous expressions, and associated concepts. Boolean operators such as **AND** and **OR** were used to establish logical relationships between the search terms and to refine the search strategy. The main search terms included **"Yoga Nidra," "geriatric population," "older adults," "cardiovascular health," "blood pressure," "heart rate variability," "psychological health," "depression," "anxiety," "stress,"** and **"mental well-being."** Different combinations of these keywords were used across the selected databases to ensure a broad and systematic retrieval of literature.

The studies retrieved from the databases were screened on the basis of their titles, abstracts, and full-text relevance. Only studies published in the **English language** between **2010 and 2026** were considered for inclusion. Research articles, review papers, and clinical studies that specifically examined **Yoga Nidra as the main intervention** and reported outcomes related to **cardiovascular health** or **psychological health** among **older adults or the geriatric population** were included in the review. Studies focused on general yoga practices without specific reference to Yoga Nidra, studies unrelated to older adults, articles not reporting cardiovascular or psychological outcomes, and duplicate or insufficiently detailed studies were excluded.

All selected studies were examined thoroughly, irrespective of methodological differences, in order to understand the therapeutic significance of Yoga Nidra in the target population. The included literature was carefully evaluated, compared, and synthesized to identify major findings related to cardiovascular parameters such as **blood pressure, heart rate, and heart rate variability**, as well as psychological variables such as **stress, anxiety, depression, cognition, and mental well-being**. The final findings were organized narratively to provide an integrated understanding of the role of Yoga Nidra in promoting cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population.

Search Outcome

The literature search for the present review yielded a total of **729 records**, of which **12 studies** were finally selected to examine the role of Yoga Nidra in improving cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population (See Table 1). The records were identified from three major electronic databases, namely **Google Scholar (n = 200), PubMed (n = 63), and ScienceDirect (n = 466)**. After the initial identification of studies, all records were screened on the basis of title, abstract, and relevance to the objectives of the review. Following this process, duplicate, irrelevant, and ineligible studies were excluded, and the remaining full-text articles were assessed according to the predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Among the **12 selected studies**, the included literature represented a range of interventional research designs, including **randomised controlled trials, single-arm interventional clinical trials, quasi-experimental interventional studies, interventional pre-post studies, and quantitative**

interventional studies. The selected studies involved different participant groups, with particular relevance to older adults and individuals with cardiovascular and psychological health concerns. The studies included in this review were published between **2010 and 2026**, in accordance with the defined time frame of the review.

The reviewed studies assessed a wide range of cardiovascular and psychological variables. Cardiovascular measures included **systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, heart rate variability, and lipid profile**, while psychological variables included **stress, anxiety, depression, sleep quality, relaxation, emotional balance, mental well-being, and quality of life**. These outcome measures served as important indicators for understanding the therapeutic role of Yoga Nidra. Overall, the findings of the included studies suggest that Yoga Nidra may serve as a beneficial supportive intervention for improving both cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population.

Review Table 01

Authors/ Year	Nature of Research Article	Study Design	Type of Intervention	Duration	Results/ Outcomes
Anjana et al. (2022) ³⁰	Randomised controlled trial	Randomized controlled parallel-group design	Om chanting combined with Yoga Nidra	2 months	This study suggests that Om chanting and Yoga Nidra may help reduce blood pressure and improve lipid profile in individuals with hypertension.
Akshita et al. (2025) ³¹	Randomised controlled trial	Randomized controlled parallel-group design	Home-based mobile-guided pranayam and Yoga Nidra meditation	24 weeks	The study suggests that simple home-based practices, such as mobile-guided pranayama and Yoga Nidra, can provide meaningful support for elderly individuals with hypertension, including helping to reduce blood pressure.
Gunjiganvi et al. (2023) ³²	Randomized controlled trial	Open-label randomized controlled trial with two parallel groups	Yoga Nidra	2 weeks	This study found that Yoga Nidra was more effective than music-based relaxation in reducing depression, anxiety, and sleep problems among frontline COVID-19 healthcare workers during stressful duty periods.
Rani K. et al. (2012) ³³	Randomized controlled trial	Randomized controlled study with intervention and control groups	Yoga Nidra	2 months	Patients with mild to moderate anxiety and depressive symptoms showed significant improvement after Yoga Nidra intervention, whereas those with severe symptoms did not show a significant change.
Markil et al. (2012) ³⁴	Randomized counter-balanced experimental trial	Randomized counter-balanced laboratory-based trial	Yoga Nidra r	Acute single-session intervention	These findings indicate a positive shift toward parasympathetic dominance. Yoga Nidra improves heart rate variability both alone and after Hatha yoga.
Rajagopalan et al. (2022) ³⁵	Prospective randomized controlled trial	Prospective randomized controlled study	Om chanting and Yoga Nidra	2 months	Om chanting and Yoga Nidra may reduce stress, improve sleep, and support blood pressure control in people with hypertension.
Ahuja et al. (2025) ²⁴	Single-arm interventional clinical trial	Pre-post single-arm	Yoga Nidra	Acute intervention (single 16-	This study highlights the positive role of Yoga Nidra in the management of essential

		intervention design		minute Yoga Nidra session)	hypertension and suggests that its effects may be explained through the Neurovisceral Integration Model.
Tanna & Khatri. (2024) ³⁶	Quasi-experimental interventional study	Pre-test-post-test single-group quasi-experimental design	Yoga Nidra	12 Yoga Nidra sessions	Yoga Nidra significantly reduces perceived stress and may also help lower blood pressure in people with hypertension, suggesting its value as a relaxation-based therapy for blood pressure control and overall well-being.
(Thangam & Bharathi. 2019) ³⁷	Quasi-experimental pre-post control design	Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest control group design	Yoga Nidra	15 days	Yoga Nidra is a simple and effective practice that may help reduce blood pressure in elderly individuals with hypertension living in old age homes.
Panigrahi et al. (2024) ³⁸	Interventional pre-post study	Pre-test-post-test single-group intervention study	Yoga Nidra with selected Pranayama	40 minutes	Regular practice of Yoga Nidra and pranayama can help older adults manage stress more effectively and foster a greater sense of calm, relaxation, and balance in everyday life.
Vashishth et al. (2024) ³⁹	Interventional pre-post study	Pre-test-post-test single-group intervention study	Yoga Nidra	45 days	The intervention led to a meaningful reduction in anxiety and stress among older adults, while also improving their sense of well-being, relaxation, sleep quality, and emotional stability. These findings suggest that Yoga Nidra can be a valuable practice for improving the overall quality of life in the elderly. compress
Pawar and Patil. (2025) ⁴⁰	Quantitative interventional study	Pre-test-post-test single-group design	Guided Yoga Nidra intervention	20 minutes	The study showed that Yoga Nidra was helpful in lowering anxiety levels among elderly people living in old age homes.

Results

Effect of Yoga Nidra on Cardiovascular Health

Yoga Nidra has shown beneficial effects on cardiovascular health, particularly in improving blood pressure regulation, autonomic balance, and related cardiovascular risk factors. The reviewed studies suggest that Yoga Nidra significantly reduces systolic and diastolic blood pressure in individuals with hypertension, indicating its supportive role in cardiovascular management. It has also been found to improve heart rate variability, which reflects enhanced parasympathetic activity and better autonomic regulation, both of which are important for healthy cardiovascular functioning [24]. In addition, some studies have reported favourable changes in lipid profile, including reductions in LDL and increases in HDL levels, suggesting that Yoga Nidra may also contribute to lowering cardiovascular risk [30].

Among older adults, Yoga Nidra-based interventions have further demonstrated positive outcomes such as reduced systolic blood pressure and improved sleep quality, supporting its usefulness as a complementary approach in the management of hypertension in the elderly [31]. A single session of Yoga Nidra has even been shown to produce immediate reductions in blood pressure along with significant improvements in HRV parameters, indicating a rapid positive influence on autonomic and cardiovascular regulation [24]. Yoga Nidra appears to improve **heart rate variability (HRV)** by

enhancing parasympathetic activity and reducing sympathetic dominance, which suggests better autonomic balance. A study found that Yoga Nidra relaxation increased HRV, and more recent evidence in hypertensive adults reported that even a single session increased HRV parameters alongside reductions in blood pressure [34]. Overall, these findings suggest that Yoga Nidra is a simple, safe, and effective mind-body practice that may help improve cardiovascular health and support blood pressure management, particularly among individuals with hypertension and older adults.

Psychological Effects of Yoga Nidra

Yoga Nidra has emerged as a promising mind-body practice for improving psychological health, particularly in relation to anxiety, depression, stress, and sleep problems. It is a guided relaxation technique that promotes deep physical, mental, and emotional rest while maintaining inner awareness. Recent evidence suggests that Yoga Nidra can significantly reduce stress, anxiety, and depressive symptoms, making it a useful supportive intervention for mental well-being [41]. Its calming effect on the nervous system may help lower mental agitation, emotional tension, and excessive worry, which are common contributors to poor psychological health. In addition, practitioners often report improved relaxation, emotional stability, mindfulness, and a greater sense of inner peace after regular practice [41,42].

Besides its effects on anxiety and depression, Yoga Nidra also appears beneficial for sleep disturbance, insomnia, psychological distress, and overall quality of life. Studies have shown that it may improve sleep quality by reducing hyperarousal and promoting a restful mental state, which is especially important for individuals experiencing chronic stress or emotional exhaustion. Some intervention studies have also found improvements in worry, anger, and mental fatigue following Yoga Nidra practice. Although current findings are encouraging, researchers emphasize the need for more well-designed and long-term trials to establish stronger evidence across diverse populations [32,43]. Overall, Yoga Nidra can be considered a simple, safe, and accessible mind-body practice that contributes to improved psychological well-being, emotional stability, and enhanced quality of life among older adults.

Conclusion

The present review concludes that Yoga Nidra is a beneficial mind-body practice for improving both cardiovascular and psychological health among the geriatric population. The available evidence suggests that it helps reduce blood pressure, improve heart rate variability, and support better autonomic regulation, thereby contributing to cardiovascular well-being. At the same time, Yoga Nidra appears effective in reducing stress, anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbances while enhancing relaxation, emotional balance, and overall mental well-being in older adults. As a simple, safe, non-invasive, and cost-effective intervention, it may serve as a valuable complementary approach in geriatric health care. However, the available evidence remains limited, and further well-designed studies are required to establish its long-term effectiveness more clearly. Overall, Yoga Nidra holds considerable potential for promoting healthy ageing and improving quality of life among older adults.

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